

Original Research

Organizational Vigor Creation Paradigm Model in Universities

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify and validate the organizational vigor creation model in the universities. In order to identify factors affecting the organizational vigor, after a focused literature review the consensus of the experts' opinion was explored. This information was placed in the form of a set of causal, intervening, axial, underlying, facilitating, strategic conditions and their outcomes by multiple coding based on grounded theory model. These data were collected from 169 experts by snowball sampling method and the hypotheses were tested. For checking validity and reliability of the designed model Smart PLS and SPSS software were used. Finally, the relationships of these variables were presented based on the path analysis model. Based on the obtained results, Organizational vigor creation model, university growth has a significant effect on the strategic management of human resources; also, strategic management of human resources, intervening conditions and organizational support in resolving work-family conflict have a significant effect on university branding, and the latter also has a positive and significant effect on the vigorous state of human resources of the universities. The results of fitting showed that the model proposed in this study has good validity and fit. The significance, implications and limitations of results have also been deliberated for further research.

Keywords: Organizational Vigor, Paradigm Model, Structural Equations.

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Introduction

The realization of any social transcreation is necessary to create vigor in the people of that society in relation to that transcreation, in order to align them with the desired goals and paths (Jovari, 2021). The characteristic of organizational vigor refers to a person when a person devotes all his strength, efforts and talents to achieve the goals and mission of the organization, sincerely and enthusiastically and without any bias (Jovari, et al., 2019). This issue has a special appearance in scientific-academic circles, because universities are the centers of creating, processing and producing knowledge and technology, their effect on the development process of countries is unique, and many new areas and concepts that enter the field of human life are originated from universities (Ghoreishi, 2019) so in recent times, the importance of the responsibility of universities has been highlighted (Ramos et al., 2020). The present study aims to design and compile a paradigm model of creating organizational vigor for human resources of the university by using the qualitative content analysis approach, because if the cycle of vigor in the university environment is disturbed due to the presence of some obstacles, the scientific development system of the country will be affected because its product cannot reflect the superior scientific-executive principles and strategies, and it cannot be expected to produce useful science and knowledge. Therefore, the present study aims to answer the question, what is the paradigm model of vigor creation in universities and how can it be introduced and explained? For this purpose, the conceptual framework has been examined according to the Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The conceptual framework of the research (proposed research model)

Literature Review

Vigor as a mode is a positive and distinct feeling that can arise from internal and external events and situations (Armon, et al., 2011: 11). When vigor is considered as a mode, attention is paid to its changes within a person in a working day; while vigor is defined as a feature with indicators such as effort, energy, flexibility and resistance to

work problems, and attention is paid to its changes among people (Wafald, et al., 2012: 5). In the Shairom model, the similar structure of Schlaflly introduces vigor as one of the components of job engagement. Shairom has criticized Schlaflly's model. He states that the vigor factor is considered as a non-ambiguous structure in Schlaflly's model. To solve these problems, Shairom introduced a multi-dimensional conceptualization of vigor, which reflects the three feelings of physical strength, emotional energy, and cognitive vigor (Shairom, et al., 2003). Contrary to Schlaflly and Shairom's model, Britt's model considers job involvement as a single-factor construct and measures it with three conceptual categories including responsibility for performance, commitment to performance, and importance of performance for the individual. (Wefald, et al., 2012: 5).

Research background

Several studies have shown that vigor acts as a mediator role in predicting individual results and outcomes, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job performance, and organizational citizenship behavior (for example: Fisher (2010: 385); Karanika, et al., (2015); Corbeanu & Iliescu (2023); Fatimah, E. P. N. (2023)). Jovari and Mohammadi Moghadam (2021) in their qualitative research introduced the inefficient conditions of laws and regulations, the abandonment of the capabilities of universities among the effective factors in intensifying the phenomenon of organizational no vigor of university members. Carmeli (2013) in presenting his final model refers to the effect of emotional intelligence on the generosity and benevolence of people through their vigor. In a comprehensive summary of the research background, it can be said that the studies conducted in the field of vigor and individual, organizational and social health are divided into five general categories: The first category is research related to the concept of vigor, which, of course, mistakenly in most of these researches, vigor is considered synonymous with happiness (for example: Silva Munar(2020); Çayak (2021); Sanamthong & Prabyai (2023); Salvadorinho &Teixeira (2023)). The second category is the studies that have examined organizational vigor as one of the components of job involvement and in the form of a sub-topic and indirectly(for example: Kong (2009), Wefald, et al., (2012); Cortes-Denia,et al.,(2023)).The third category is researches that have paid attention to the outcomes and results of people's vigor and health from the perspective of individual psychology and personal life, ignoring this phenomenon in the organizational environment(for example: Akhavan Sarraf, et al., (2017); Sepahvand & Bagherzadeh Khodashahri (2021); Azike, et al., (2023)). In the fourth category of research (for example: Cortés-Denia, et al., (2023); Alkorashy & Alanazi (2023), Abduraimi, et al., (2023)) the comparison of the state of social vigor and health in different cities with a social and sociological approach can be seen, which beyond the statistical relationship between variables, no other analysis of the state of social vigor has been done, and only the level of happiness and vigor and the effective factors have been examined. In the fifth category, which has more semantic affinity with the topic and context of the present study, the category of vigor has been analyzed from the perspective of obstacles and outcomes (for example: Anaza, et al., (2016); Corbeanu & Iliescu (2023); Sypniewska, et al., (2023)). Therefore, the factors affecting the vigor of employees are divided into four levels of job, organizational, managerial and welfare factors (material and spiritual) and then each of these factors is divided into three more detailed categories called sub-factors at a lower level. one of the things that can be found in this study is that in the mentioned researches, the criteria of measurements were two standard questionnaires of

organizational vigor by Pryce-Jones (2011) and Kjerulf (2007)(Jovari, et al., 2020; 2019). Considering that every person has his own spiritual and psychological world and also considering the socio-cultural and ideological differences between countries, cities, villages, neighborhoods and even families, the question that arises is whether to measure the state of vigor of people with a fixed measure is also correct based on non-Iranian research with distinct cultures.

Fig. 2. Factors related to organizational vigor (extracted from research literature)

Research method

The present study is practical in terms of purpose and descriptive-exploratory in terms of method. To collect data, the method of studying theoretical foundations and past researches, in-depth and semi-structured interviews, and questionnaires were used. In order to examine the pattern of vigor and relationships between conditions, contexts and factors, this questionnaire was compiled based on the categories counted in the interview section of the research. The community of interviewees were 20 university members who have the highest experimental and scientific creation regarding the issues related to this study (the scope of this study), while having a wide range of opinions and deep knowledge. This means that in this field, they have records and educational background, scientific works (books, articles), teaching or research records, or related positions and executive records, or in this field (for example, in the field of human resources management, educational sciences, and organizational psychology, strategic and operational program of the university) make decisions. Therefore, the sampling method in the present study was non-random and purposive method, during which people with specific characteristics in terms of scientific and experimental records and having the necessary communication skills to participate and influence the research were selected. Emphasis on the membership in the specialized working group of the strategic and operational program of the university, academic degree and work experience has been in order to express the individual's opinion based on organizational knowledge and the data are reliable. At the beginning, in order to achieve a common understanding of the content of the interview, the desired concept of vigor was explained to the participants based on the findings of the literature review and the background of the research. The vigor of human resources of the university is a state of positivity, satisfaction and intellectual flexibility in university members, which leads to the activity and expenditure of additional educational, research and executive energy, in order to voluntarily participate in the realization of individual and organizational goals. In these interviews, the questions were

formulated and adjusted according to the grounded theory, and gradually, according to the progress and conduct of the initial interviews, these questions became more comprehensive. The data obtained from semi-structured interviews with academic experts were analyzed using the grounded theory method. To study the hypotheses, the quantitative phase of the research was based on the data that was collected using a researcher-made questionnaire. This questionnaire was collected from 169 experts by snowball sampling method and was obtained based on the dimensions and subcategories identified in the first phase. The questionnaire included 17 dimensions and 73 items. After ensuring the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, the variable measurement tool was distributed among the members of the statistical sample. In this study, the partial least square method was used to test the hypotheses. Finally, by using PLS Smart software, the conceptual model of the research has been measured and the construct validity has been determined.

Findings

40.24% and 59.76% of respondents are male and female, respectively. The number of students, professors, managers, and experts in respondents are 4.14%, 37.27%, and 13.01% and 24.85%, respectively. 49.11% and 50.89% of respondents are single and married, respectively, whose age range is between 20 to 30 years to over 50 years. The age range of the respondents in 20 to 30 years old, 31 to 40 years old, 41 to 50 years old and over 50 years old are 39.05%, 34.19%, 13.02% and 13.02%, respectively. Therefore, the lowest frequency of age in the sample volume is 41 to 50 years and above 50 years and the highest frequency of age in the target sample volume is 20 to 30 years.

University growth, strategic management of human resources, positive psychological characteristics in members, extra-university restrictions, intra-university restrictions, support in resolving work-family conflicts, brand-referencing of university capabilities, university is responsive of a set of causal, intervening, strategic, axial, underlying, facilitative. How these categories are related was proposed in the form of a paradigm model according to Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Organizational vigor creation model for human resources of the university

According to the proposed classification based on the opinion of experts, the research hypotheses were introduced as follows:

H₁: the university growth (Causal conditions) has a positive and significant effect on the strategic management of human resources (Axial phenomenon).

H₂: strategic management of human resources (axial phenomenon) has a positive and significant effect on university branding (Strategies).

H3: Intervening condition has a positive and significant effect on university branding (S).

H4: organizational support in resolving work-family conflict (Underlying conditions) has a positive and significant effect on university branding (S).

H5: the university branding (S) has a positive and significant effect on the vigor and responsiveness (Outcomes).

Measurable models goodness fit (outer model)

In face validity, the appearance of the questionnaire is examined in terms of editing, shape, spelling, etc., before its distribution. In this study, the questionnaire was reviewed by several university professors and some organizational experts (higher education authorities) before distribution, and the researcher designed and edited the questionnaire after applying their correction comments.

Table 1. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) criterion

Latent variables	AVE>0.5
Cc	0.693
AC	0.684
Ic	0.706
Uc	0.650
S	0.720
O	0.756

As can be seen in Table 1, all the AVEs for the latent variables of the research model are greater than 0.5 and therefore the measurement model has appropriate convergent validity.

To check the discriminant (divergent) validity of the measurement model, the Fornell and Larker criterion shows the degree of correlation of a construct with its indicators compared to the correlation of that construct with other constructs.

Table 2. Fornell and Larker criterion

Variable code	S	Uc	Cc	Ac	Ap	O
S	0.681					
Uc	0.606	0.764				
Cc	0.533	0.629	0.765			
Ic	0.595	0.692	0.737	0.744		
Ap	0.618	0.750	0.711	0.675	0.683	
O	0.668	0.684	0.580	0.636	0.611	0.676

As Table 2, the square root of AVE on the main diameter is greater than the values of other variables so it can be said that the discriminant validity test is confirmed.

According to Table 3, the values of all variables are more than 0.7, and the appropriate goodness fit of the measurement models has been confirmed; therefore, the measurement model has good reliability.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha coefficient and composite reliability of the research latent variables

Latent variables	Cronbach's alpha (Alpha>0.7)	Composite reliability (CR>0.7)
Cc	0.769	0.837
Ac	0.825	0.875
Ic	0.836	0.877
Uc	0.879	0.901
S	0.770	0.839
O	0.765	0.834

Table 4. Bartlett's and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test

Significance level	Degrees of freedom	Bartlett's chi-square	KMO
0.000	820	4.12	0.903

Table 4 shows the KMO value of 0.903 of a high and appropriate value (greater than 0.5), which is the first condition for the validity of factor analysis. Also, in Bartlett's test, the chi-square value has been obtained 4.12, which is significant with a significance level of 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and the other condition of validity of the factor analysis is established.

Table 5. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnov test statistics	Significance level	Test result
Cc	1/34	0/05	Normal
Ac	1/39	0/13	
Ic	1/14	0/14	
Uc	1/14	0/14	
S	1/21	0/10	
O	1/34	0/05	

According to the results of Table 5, because the value of the significance level for all variables is greater than the error level of $\alpha=0.05$ ($p<0.05$); as a result, the research variables have a normal distribution and parametric tests can be used to test the research hypotheses.

Fig. 4. The structural equation model with path coefficients

Fig. 5. The structural equation model with significant coefficients

In Fig. 4, the path coefficients or beta coefficient (β) of the research model are specified. The values of significant coefficients (T-values) of the research model are also shown in Fig. 4. Other outputs of the software that can be seen in Fig. 4 are R2 coefficients, which are included in the circle of each endogenous latent variable. The factor loading value of each of the observed variables for the corresponding latent variable is the minimum acceptable value of 0.4.

Table 6. Standardized factor loadings and t-coefficients between model classes

Variables	Factor loading	T-values	Result
C c	0.728	17.928	Significant
	0.654	11.977	
	0.714	14.446	
	0.701	14.077	
	0.742	18.386	
	0.798	25.045	
	0.628	10.747	
Ap	0.637	10.791	
	0.607	10.543	
	0.743	18.701	
	0.648	11.293	
	0.743	17.285	
	0.711	13.365	
Ic	0.620	11.186	
	0.724	18.317	
	0.705	15.007	
	0.638	9.726	
	0.710	15.657	
	0.577	9.190	
	0.573	9.201	
	0.640	9.410	
	0.744	14.123	
	0.760	16.388	
	0.701	10.577	
Uc	0.706	11.621	
	0.798	23.051	
	0.685	11.558	
	0.825	24.011	
	0.796	21.157	
S	0.710	15.026	
	0.684	11.566	
	0.582	8.427	
	0.699	16.391	
	0.727	15.345	
	0.671	11.907	
O	0.671	12.477	
	0.648	11.844	
	0.630	8.549	
	0.675	10.624	
	0.721	12.794	
	0.705	16.196	

In Table 6. As can be seen, T-values and standardized factor loading between the items and their related latent variables in all cases are calculated to be greater than 1.96 and 0.4, respectively in level 0.000.

Structural model goodness fit (inner model)

A) As can be seen in Fig. 5, all paths have a significance coefficient greater than 1.96, so all paths are confirmed for the research model.

B) R^2 criterion, the second criterion for checking the goodness fit of the structural model in research is R^2 coefficients related to endogenous (dependent) latent variables of the model.

According to Table 7, the R^2 value confirms the appropriateness of the goodness fit of the structural model according to the three criterion values.

Table 7. The results of R^2 and the main endogenous variables

Main endogenous variables	R^2	R^2 Adjusted
S	0.449	0.439
Ap	0.585	0.583
O	0.589	0.587

C) As can be seen in Table 8, the contribution of exogenous variables to the endogenous variables of the research model is strong.

Table 8. The results of f^2

Independent variable	Dependent variable	f^2
Ap	Strategies	0.41
Ic		0.37
Uc		0.48

The results of Table 9 show all variables are higher than 0.35 and indicate strong predictive power for the structure and model, the appropriate predictive power of the model regarding the endogenous constructs of the research and confirm the appropriate goodness fit of the structural model. Total model goodness fit with the GOF criterion, for the GOF criterion of 0.392, the very appropriate goodness fit of the total model for the research is confirmed.

Table 9. Q^2 coefficients of endogenous variables

Endogenous variables	Q^2
S	0.360
Ap	0.362
O	0.364

In Table 10, the results of the research hypothesis test in the structural equation model are introduced.

Table 10. The results of the research hypothesis test

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Path	Path coefficient	Path coefficient	Significance level	Test result
Cc	Ap	university growth → strategic management of human resources	0.765	23.570	0.000	Confirmed, positive and significant
Ap	S	strategic management of human resources → university branding	0.258	2.290	0.022	
Ic	S	restrictive intervening and facilitating condition → university branding	0.224	2.544	0.011	
Uc	S	support in resolving work-family conflict → university branding	0.258	2.382	0.018	
S	O	university branding →vigor and responsiveness of university	0.768	27.397	0.000	

The size of the T-value of the path related to university growth and the strategic management of human resources was found to be 23.570 and because this value is greater than the value of the critical value of 1.96, the effect of university growth on the strategic management of human resources was found to be significant at the error level of $\alpha=0.05$, and due to the positiveness of the path coefficient (0.765), this relationship is direct and positive. In the study of the relationship between the Ap of the organizational vigor creation model in the university and strategic actions, i.e. the strategic management of human resources and the university branding respectively, the significance coefficient (T-value) of this path is 2.290 and because this value is greater than the critical value of 1.96 is, the effect of strategic management of human resources on university branding is significant at the error level of $\alpha=0.05$, and considering the positiveness of the path

coefficient (0.258), this relationship is direct and positive. The size of the significance coefficient (T-value) of the path of restrictive and facilitating conditions and university branding's capabilities as axial conditions and strategic actions for the organizational vigor creation model in the university was obtained equal to 2.544 and since this value is greater than the critical value of 1.96, the effect of members' positive psychological capacities on university branding is significant at the error level of $\alpha=0.05$, and considering the positiveness of the path coefficient (0.224), this relationship is direct and positive. In other words, the calculated significance level (0.000) is smaller than the error level of $\alpha=0.05$ ($p < 0.05$). As a result, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be said that the positive psychological capacities of the members are effective on the university branding. In examining the relationship between the underlying conditions of support in resolving work-family conflict on the model strategy, i.e. university branding's capabilities, the significance coefficient (T-value) of this path was found to be 2.382, and since this value is greater than the critical value of 1.96, the effect of the conditions of the underlying conditions of the model on the action of the strategy of this model is significant at the error level of $\alpha=0.05$ and considering the positiveness of the path coefficient (0.258), this relationship is direct and positive, that is, with a confidence of 0.95%, it can be said that the support of the university in resolving work-family conflict is effective on the university branding. In examining the relationship between the action of the model and its outcome, i.e. the effect of university branding on the vigor and responsiveness of this university, the significance coefficient (T-value) of this path was found to be 2.290, and since this value is greater than the critical value of 1.96, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be said that the university branding's capabilities (with a path coefficient of 0.258) will be the basis for a vigorous and responsive outcome in the university.

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research to design the organizational vigor creation model for universities and evaluating its validity a set of causal, intervening, axial, strategies, underlying, facilitating, conditions and their outcomes were investigated by a triangulation method as follows:

Causal conditions include university growth contains growth in the quality evaluation and assurance system, collaborative decision making, growth of regulations, growth of work and welfare facilities.

Intervening factors include facilitating and limiting intervening conditions. Facilitating intervening conditions contains positive individual psychological characteristics (hopeful, optimism sense of efficiency, intellectual flexibility) and positive professional psychological characteristics (educational-research dynamics, participation in the realization of university goals, adherence to the principles of professional ethics); limiting intervening conditions external conditions (university depreciation against, upstream policies, international sanctions) and internal conditions structural deficiencies (ignoring motivational issues, inefficiency of laws and regulations and emergence of anti-productive behaviors).

Axial conditions: strategic management of human resources contains development and cultivation of talents (identifying university talents, talent development, maintenance of

specialist personnel) and design and establishment of succession (selection and appointment based on competence of members, training and development of competence of members, using performance evaluation results in promotion).

Underlying conditions contains resolving work-family conflict (family support for the member's employment, sympathetic organizational atmosphere among members, and organizational support for multiple member roles).

Strategies include branding the capabilities of the university to the target population (internationalization of university achievements, expansion of national-international research interactions, sharing knowledge and experience).

Outcomes include vigorous being on an individual level (development of positive psychological characteristics in members, development of educational-research activities of members) and vigorous being at the organizational level (increasing the quality of educational-research and breeding services, entrepreneurship- the third generation of the university).

For explaining the mentioned items it can be said based on the obtained results, in organizational vigor creation paradigm model the members of universities want the university to become less bureaucratic because in recent years, it is felt that the university has suffered bureaucratic inferiority and this causes confusion in the realization of the goals and mission of the university and also if a precise and appropriate conceptualization of the bureaucratic processes is done for the members, the lack of organizational vigorous in them will be reduced. In matching this part of the research findings with the research background, the following cases can be mentioned: Javdani (2014) also identified the bureaucratic, inflexible organizational environment, misplaced official procedures and the promotion of administrative paperwork among the obstacles in designing the model of organizational development in Iran's higher education system. Malekinia, et al; (2014) considered the participation of university stakeholders in decision-making to foster critical thinking skills and a symbol of a sustainable university (Jovari & Mohammadi moghadam 2021). In the present study, the strategic management of human resources in the context of the organizational university model means the design and establishment of succession management, as well as the development of a comprehensive plan of human resources in order to flourish and cultivate talents for each member, and through benefiting from the capabilities and the expertise of the members will be implemented in the administration of scientific-executive affairs and the promotion of the human resources system. The issue of succession in educational organizations is of double importance because the output of educational organizations is used as the input of other organizations. In educational organizations, there is competition in the field of attracting and maintaining talented managers and employees and developing their skills. Also, the departure of people from various levels of the organization for various reasons such as resignation, retirement, job promotion or even death is inevitable, and if there is no systematic and planned solution to fill the empty place caused by the absence of these people, especially among faculty members, the university will be faced with issues such as academic decline of students, stress of professors, research defects, key positions being vacant or these positions being filled with people without the necessary talent and competence. The research of Bamdad Sufi and Imamat (2018) entitled identification and

prioritization of factors affecting the attraction and retention of scientific talents in the university, have emphasized the need for universities to try to attract and cultivate talents. In the Price and Jones (2010) model, the core of the member's vigor is nothing but a person's feeling of the flourishing and actualization of his individual talents.

In continuation of the process of the paradigm model of this study, as intervening conditions, the positive psychological capacities of university members in the individual and organizational dimensions include individual positive psychological characteristics such as hope, optimism, sense of efficacy, flexibility, ethics, as well as positive professional psychological characteristics such as educational-research dynamics, participation in the realization of university goals, adherence to the principles of professional ethics were considered as effective factors in the vigorous model of university members. With the empowerment of communication, reluctance and lack of scientific courage and organizational stagnation give way to dynamism and production of science instead of imitation, that is, we will face scientific dynamics and knowledge production. The studies can be stated in confirmation of the mentioned findings such as Stajkovic & Luthans (1998) found a positive and significant relationship between self-efficacy and performance indicators by conducting a meta-analysis. If we understand the feeling of efficacy as a person's belief about the ability to succeed in a task, then optimism is an expectation related to future success. Luthans & Youssef (2007) also confirmed the relationship between optimism and employee performance in the healthcare and banking industries. Snyder (2002) showed that people who have more hope not only have a firm determination to achieve the goal, but also consider multiple paths and methods to achieve the goal and have a special ability to anticipate obstacles and challenges. Also, organizations that have more hopeful employees are more profitable, and more hopeful managers have work units with better performance (Yazdanshenas & Mazidabadi, 2015). Luthans (2007) recognized the positive psychological capital of members as a motivational basis for the organizational productivity of members (Yildiz, 2019). Also, Arab et al. (2016) have proven the effect of positive organizational ethics on meeting the growth needs of employees and also creating a sense of energy in members.

One of the challenges identified in order to create vigor for women working in universities was the lack of sufficient support in the attitudinal and behavioral aspects of their personal and family responsibilities from the university. To solve this challenge, the strategy of raising the role of women and family by the university authorities was confirmed by the experts. In the organizational strategy of raising the status of women and the family, it is important to improve the positive attitude of the university and the family towards the valuableness of multiple family and organizational roles of women in the university. A change in values, beliefs and attitude will lead to a change in individual, family and organizational behavior. In this strategy, raising the status of women and family based on synergistic and coordinating organizational mechanisms between the family and organizational roles of members is proposed, because due to the complex and sometimes overlapping roles of working women, their job vigor can be obtained on the basis of mental images and their evaluation and perception of the degree of harmony between the quality of their organizational and personal life. University authorities should be determined with a holy perspective on the noble roles of women, to revise the internal rules and bylaws of the university in the areas of working hours and how to manage working time by insisting on meritocracy and emphasizing on their great mission in

raising university-educated girls and mothers, while creating a context for ensuring the social roles of the members on their more preferable role as mothers and wives to create self-confidence. At the least possible, it is enough for the members and their families to imagine that the main priority of the university is the individual and family vigor of the members that is when the university faces the efficient and double intellectual participation and energy of the members. However most of the researches conducted in the field of human resources and positive organizational behavior have focused on concepts such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, depression analysis, etc (Ennida & Allouani (2023); Warnabarana & Randika (2022); Alkaser (2022); Rosafizah, et al; (2020); Hossain (2020)) or studying anti-productive and stressful organizational behaviors(Yaman& Yaman (2023); Omasu et al. (2022); Ghita, et al;(2022); Privitera (2020)) but current research shows that these variables play a significant role in explaining the individual and organizational consequences of positive organizational behaviors and the phenomenon of organizational vigor has a good predictive power in predicting the occurrence of these behaviors. Therefore, by creating mutual understanding between the members and the organization, the university becomes the foundation for the vigor of the members and their families, and ultimately the health of the organization will be met. Heydari (2017) mentioned the mutual influence of organizational vigor and family vigor of members. In addition to the task of educating students, academics also have a responsibility in the legal, environmental, moral and altruistic fields under the title of social responsibility that is, meeting the needs of the local community. Branding is in services of mechanism used to introduce services and differentiate them in the competitive market. The action of university referencing is like a change strategy that marks a change in beliefs, values and attitudes, with the support of senior managers of this system, it can spread a dynamic and sustainable change process to the higher education system (Javdani, 2014). It can be said that it is necessary for university members to interact and show their capabilities to the target population in order to create platforms for scientific-executive dynamics for them in the target population. Bamdad Sufi and Imamat (2018) entitled identification and prioritization of factors affecting the attraction and retention of scientific talents in the university, has emphasized the efforts of universities in order to build a brand based on the attraction and cultivation of talents, and with the aim of presenting a better image of their university in competitive markets, they have proposed to strengthen the cooperation of each university with the academic network and commercial organizations. Hajipour and Soltani (2014) pointing out that universities are facing a complex and turbulent environment, is considered the correct guidance of universities dependent on the correct knowledge and understanding of the environment and its developments, as well as the use of strategic planning models based on environmental opportunities and internal strengths. Noorshahi (2014) listed the foundation for interactions along with the reputation of the university, among the indicators for measuring the quality of university services. Ghahramani, et al ;(2017) found the acquisition of extra-university and transnational identity to be effective in gaining reputation and social prestige from the university of the place of service also they recognized the connection of the university member with the industry as an effective factor for growth and serving the society.

Scientific-practical suggestions

The foundation of a resource-oriented view towards academic members causes the member to evaluate and judge the fairness.

To design training courses on strategies for creating the categories of organizational health and vigor and spirituality, as well as creating think tanks in the organization in order to apply the categories of organizational health and vigor and spirituality.

In order to introduce the capabilities of the members to the target population, develop the university more in the region and thus support the vigor of its members.

Suggestions for future researchers

It is recommended to include more variables in the conceptual model in the future research.

It is also recommended to implement and institutionalize the final research model in universities and other knowledge-based companies in order to improve the model.

Limitations

This study, has limitations such as the limited statistical population, and therefore caution should be observed in generalizing its results.

Lack of scientific resources that have examined the concept of vigor separately from the topic of happiness.

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